

ENVRI-Hub

NEXT

D7.1

Report on Metadata Catalogue Development

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Abstract**Keywords**

Metadata Catalogue, FAIRness, API, ECV/EXV

Deliverable 7.1 describes the rationale and the architecture of the Catalogue of Services and its implementation up to the first half of the project. Three main parts are described: metadata schema and ingestion, front-end ad hoc improvements, back-end structure and APIs available. The Catalogue of Services is at the same time a tool for the final user, scientist or decision maker, a showcase for other hub components and a resource repository for machine-to-machine harvesting and enquiries. Planned work and future developments are highlighted among the conclusions.

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Terminology / Acronyms (in order of appearance)	
Term/Acronym	Definition
CoS	Catalogue of Services
API	Application Programming Interface (a set of routines, protocols, and tools for building software applications)
EHN	ENVRI-Hub NEXT
FDP	Fair Data Points
DCAT-AP	Data Catalog Vocabulary - Application Profile
EPOS-DCAT-AP	EPOS extension of DCAT-AP
EPOS	European Plate Observing System
RI	Research Institute
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
ECV	Essential Climate Variable
EXV	Essential Variable concepts in domains such as Climate, Ocean and Biodiversity sciences
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ENVRI	Community of Environmental Research Infrastructures
REST	Representational State Transfer
GUI	Graphical User Interface
AF	Analytical Framework
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure

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Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	7
2. Technical Background.....	9
2.1. FAIRness and a Focus on Interoperability.....	10
2.2. EPOS platform: an Open-Source Framework for managing Data Services.....	12
2.3. Developing CoS using the EPOS Open-Source Platform.....	13
3. Metadata Collection.....	16
3.1. Catalogue of Services Metadata.....	16
3.2. Maintenance and Growth.....	16
3.3. Collaborations with other WPs and Future Steps.....	17
3.4. Back Office.....	18
4. Back-end Operations: API and Data Conversion.....	19
4.1. Converter Component.....	19
4.1.1. Overview.....	19
4.1.2. Converter Applicability.....	19
4.1.3. Architecture.....	19
4.1.4. Plugin Management.....	21
4.2. CoS APIs.....	22
4.2.1. A Federated API Ecosystem: RIs and CoS APIs.....	22
4.2.2. Applying RESTful Principles to the ENVRI Context.....	22
4.2.3. Inferred API Functionality: A User's Perspective.....	23
5. Conclusions.....	25
6. References.....	26

Table of Figures

- [Figure 1 - CoS Architecture inherited from the EPOS Open-Source Web page](#)
- [Figure 2 - CV Filter Mockup](#)
- [Figure 3 - ECV Templates Mockup](#)

Executive Summary

The present deliverable focuses on the first release of the metadata catalogue component of the ENVRI-Hub within the ENVRI-Hub NEXT (EHN) project. The main goal of this component is to help users find and access data services. These data services are encouraged to improve their interoperability and reusability by the standard metadata schema, the API structure and generically by the architectural choices made in the design phase of the catalogue and of its internal modules.

We refer to this catalogue as the Catalogue of Services (CoS), to distinguish it from other catalogues in the project, such as the catalogue of data based on Fair Data Points (FDP). The CoS metadata schema relies on a well-established¹ extension of the DCAT-AP application profile [R1], namely EPOS-DCAT-AP [R2]. RIs (or equivalent service providers) were encouraged to start with EPOS-DCAT-AP as their first enforcement of the FAIR principles with a particular focus on the encoding of ECVs [R3]. However, the quality of the metadata (and therefore the accessibility of those services) requires constant monitoring of those service endpoints and continuous improvement. This first release of CoS includes services with both high-quality metadata and less accurate descriptions, which need to be improved in the second half of the project.

The development of CoS is based on the EPOS open source project [R4] with improvements aiming at addressing Essential Climate Variables (ECVs)². The first CoS release provides dedicated search and visualization functionality as well as pre-configured examples of service usage in the ENVRI-Hub platform.

This deliverable describes the challenges and the approach adopted in the CoS to overcome them, the metadata collection and ingestion, the back-end modules of the application and some front-end features in CoS. We refer to other deliverables where related topics are more deeply described:

- [D5.1](#) for the architecture of the whole hub
- [D7.2](#) for the connection between the CoS and the Analytical Framework
- [D7.3](#) for a quick user guide of the CoS interface
- [D7.4](#) and [D7.5](#) for the connection with the FDPs

¹

<https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/collection/semic-support-centre/successful-implementation-dcat-ap-epos-foster-interoperability>

² The project is also considering their generalization in different domain EXVs (where the "X" means that not only climate variables are included).

1. Introduction

The ENVRI-Hub NEXT (EHN) project addresses significant challenges in environmental data management and aims to provide an integrated framework for enabling interdisciplinary research. The project identified the barriers that hinder scientists from effectively working with environmental data, particularly Essential Climate Variables (ECVs):

- **Discovery Barrier:** It is difficult to find relevant data from diverse, distributed sources that often employ different metadata schemas or vocabularies, requiring substantial human effort to navigate and select appropriate datasets;
- **Access Barrier:** Accessing data from multiple sources is challenging if they do not share common interfaces, protocols, or harmonized access controls, which impedes human and machine-to-machine interactions;
- **Composition Barrier:** Data often resides behind unhomogenized service interfaces; customized, ad-hoc, integrations are required in workflow applications, which makes the reusability limited, due to extensive code adaptation;
- **Processing Barrier:** Analyzing ECVs often requires data from different infrastructures, where automating workflows with distributed data sources on remote infrastructure remains a challenge;
- **Usability Barrier:** The steep learning curve associated with new data and computing technologies and the low (re)usability of tools across different application domains, hinder researchers from effectively using these resources in their daily practices.

Besides these general obstacles, we also have to address other technical and practical issues. The quality of metadata needs continuous monitoring and improvement. There is also a need for harmonisation of metadata between providers and products, including service catalogues and data catalogues, to ensure interoperability. Reference architectures and interoperability frameworks, such as FAIR best practices and EOSC technical guidelines, are still evolving, while many existing services do not support REST-like APIs, complicating their description using common standards like EPOS-DCAT-AP.

The EHN project's primary purpose, therefore, revolves around overcoming these challenges to facilitate interdisciplinary environmental research. To consolidate and advance the ENVRI-Hub's robust conceptual and technical structure, enabling the ENVRI Science Cluster to provide interdisciplinary data-driven services that support climate change research, mitigation, adaptation, and risk assessment. It also aims to integrate the environmental science community into the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), guided by the concept of Essential Climate Variables (ECVs).

The Catalogue of Services (CoS) serves as a **centralized entryway for finding and accessing data and services from Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRIs)**, facilitating their discovery and reuse through its architectural design. The CoS implements a combined interoperability approach by leveraging semantically rich metadata to describe web services, enabling homogeneous access through advanced software that uses semantic crosswalks for parameter mappings. It natively supports **FAIR principles** (Findability, Accessibility,

Interoperability, Reusability) by design, and it promotes harmonization of metadata standards across communities, based on success practices on EPOS-DCAT-AP, an extension of DCAT-AP, developed in EPOS. The initial extension introduced metadata elements for representing services, their endpoints, parameters, and relationships with datasets. With the release of DCAT-AP versions 2 and 3, the specification introduced the concept of DataService, improving its capability to describe web-based access points.

The CoS provides multiple interfaces, including a graphical user interface (GUI) for human users and an API gateway for machine-to-machine interactions. A so-called "Backoffice" application is being developed to simplify metadata management, allowing users to create, edit, and delete service metadata descriptions via an intuitive graphical interface. The CoS acts as a showcase for other Hub components, like FAIR Data Points (FDPs), and a resource repository for harvesting and enquiries, e.g. from other aggregators either at the HUB level or from other systems such as EOSC. It strengthens connections with other EHN components, such as the Analytical Framework (AF) and the Knowledge Base.

The architecture of the CoS comprises several internal microservices as depicted in [Figure 1](#). However, the three main entities are:

- **Metadata Database:** Stores metadata for services, data, and products provided by research infrastructures. Those services include highly heterogeneous web services, some inherited from the ENVRI-FAIR project metadata descriptions, and new additions like IOC Sealevel Monitoring Station List³, ERDDAP Web Service for accessing Argo Float⁴, and EISCAT Madrigal database⁵;
- **API Gateway:** Enables external agents to use advanced functionalities for data access through REST APIs;
- **Graphical User Interfaces (GUI):** Offers a map-based portal and lists of cataloged services with semantic-driven search functionalities (some of them are common to all services, while each service can have dedicated advanced filters). The GUI can dynamically construct queries and render results on an interactive map if the service response is in a supported format (e.g., GeoJSON) or a data conversion plugin is available. Otherwise, the GUI will display the metadata provided and the link to the data source.

³ <http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org>

⁴ <https://erddap.ifremer.fr/erddap/tabledap/ArgoFloats.html>

⁵ <https://cedar.openmadrigal.org/openmadrigal>

Figure 1: CoS Architecture inherited from the EPOS Open Source Web Page⁶

⁶ <https://epos-eu.github.io/epos-open-source/#/>

2. Technical Background

In this chapter, we analyze the integration complexity, which is the main requirement for the CoS architecture. We introduce the EPOS open source platform and discuss how it fits the challenge and how it has been adopted and integrated in the ENVRI-Hub

The aforementioned barriers preventing scientists from efficiently working with Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) are related to discovery, access, composition, processing and usability. FAIRifying the data and services using a Catalogue of Services (CoS) is thus crucial. The key requirement is to enable the integration of data coming from heterogeneous sources in different formats. In order to support the project goal to homogenise access to data, related descriptions and services (see also D11.2 for instance), the CoS addresses these issues using the successful practices from EPOS for Solid Earth Science.

The development of the Catalogue of Services (CoS) within the ENVRI-Hub NEXT (EHN) project is guided by several key requirements to ensure it effectively supports interdisciplinary environmental research.

First and foremost, the CoS needs to provide **centralized and federated access** to data services. The CoS must serve as a centralized entryway for accessing data and services from RIs. It should be a federated system of harmonized subdomain/RI-specific systems, ensuring modularity, scalability; being open source is a plus value. It needs to make services and datasets available for Virtual Research Environments (VREs) and Graphical User Interfaces (GUIs).

The open source release of the EPOS code is synchronized with the production one; therefore, the Catalogue of Services inherits the stability and the maturity level of a widely adopted platform, and, moreover, the federation between ENVRI-Hub and EPOS is straightforward. Besides this, however, the CoS has been further developed to fulfil the needs of the ENVRI community.

The main components of the CoS have already been introduced in the introduction, and they will be further elaborated in the following sections. In Figure 1 appears also other micro-services that are essential for the overall operations of the CoS, but they are less interesting. We briefly recall them here:

- **Ingestor:** It is the module that injects the metadata files into the CoS database;
- **Resources:** it is the module that handles all other resource files besides metadata;
- **External Access:** It manages the queries to external services;
- **TCS Services:** This is an EPOS-related jargon, where the Tematic Core Services (TCS) represent the data/service providers; in the ENVRI environment, this module corresponds to the RIs' data services.

Metadata needs **harmonization** both between data providers and between data products, a common DCAT profile for RI-service APIs and RI-Fair Data Point (FDP) APIs should be defined. RIs should use, as a first step towards FAIR principles, metadata described in EPOS-DCAT-AP. The metadata provision should be facilitated in order to lower the entry barrier for new data

providers; a back-office graphical interface should replace the effort to manually redact Turtle files⁷.

The CoS should provide a graphic user interface (GUI) for **human access**, including map-based portals and lists of cataloged datasets. The GUI needs to incorporate semantic-driven search functionalities that enable users to search using controlled vocabularies. The GUI should allow users to dynamically construct queries to web services by configuring parameters. It should feature a filter to highlight services related to selected Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) and support pre-configured, shareable thematic views of the portal.

An **API gateway** is required to enable external agents to use the catalogue's advanced functionalities for data access, supporting standards like REST APIs, OAI-PMH, and DCAT-related standards. Interfaces need to be developed to achieve interoperability between the CoS and selected AF use cases, validated through prototypes like Jupyter Notebooks.

2.1. FAIRness and a Focus on Interoperability

Catalogues, data portals, and all other forms of aggregation of scientific data share similar features while relying on different approaches and architectures. FAIR principles are nowadays widely accepted in the scientific domain, and their application can be monitored by dedicated metrics. The CoS integrates all these good practices and stands out in particular for what concerns interoperability. Its main requirement indeed is to allow users to aggregate and analyze data from different sources and disciplines, being a centralized and federated entry point.

The interoperability approaches usually followed by catalogues and data portals can be classified into four main categories:

- The **data approach** focuses on the physical representation of facts, aiming to harmonize the variety of data formats and representations prevalent in interdisciplinary settings. This approach seeks to create a unified and standardised representation through either the convergence of similar data towards the same standardized formats or by implementing conversion or mapping processes across different existing formats. A key advantage is the potential for a unified view and simplified processing once data is harmonized. However, this method necessitates significant coordination and consensus among the various stakeholders involved. Furthermore, the actual conversion of datasets towards a common format can be a time-consuming and resource-intensive process;
- The **metadata approach** centers on data that describes other data, providing crucial contextual information like source, format, authorship, and quality, thereby enhancing data understandability and manageability. A significant advantage of this approach is that it improves data management by making data more discoverable and understandable and by offering insights into data provenance and usage. By specifying data standards and formats, metadata ensures adherence to common conventions, facilitating machine readability. Interoperability is achieved by providing context and details about the data without directly altering the data itself. However, successful implementation requires the adoption of commonly accepted metadata standards (e.g.,

⁷ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Turtle_\(syntax\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Turtle_(syntax))

Dublin Core) or the development of custom standards that can be interpreted by different machines. Moreover, it is essential to define mappings between different metadata schemas or standards to ensure compatibility across sources. This approach also requires ongoing efforts for metadata creation and continuous curation to maintain its accuracy and relevance;

- The **semantic approach** focuses on defining the meaning of (meta)data elements, the relationships between data, and their intended use. Semantic interoperability is achieved by encoding knowledge in a machine-readable format through vocabularies and ontologies, enabling understanding beyond mere syntax. Systems leveraging this approach can perform sophisticated semantic queries that consider the meaning and context of data, leading to more precise and relevant data retrieval. Nevertheless, creating or adopting ontologies is an effort-consuming task. Additionally, both ontologies and semantic mappings require continuous maintenance to remain up-to-date and accurate. Examples of semantic standards include Schema.org and SKOS (Simple Knowledge Organization System);
- The **web service approach** offers interoperability through standardized machine-to-machine software interfaces hosted at network-addressable locations. A key benefit is that a web service acts as an interface that hides the implementation details, allowing it to be used independently of the underlying hardware, software, or programming language. Interoperability through web services necessitates agreeing on a communication protocol, commonly SOAP (Simple Object Access Protocol) or REST (Representational State Transfer), and selecting a Request/Response Format, typically XML or JSON (JavaScript Object Notation). In some cases, agreements on using the same web service interface might be needed. However, achieving consensus on these aspects can be challenging, particularly in a multidisciplinary context with diverse technological preferences and requirements.

A combined approach designed to handle heterogeneous datasets is implemented in the CoS. Recognizing that web services often implement various standard protocols and provide data in different formats, this approach leverages semantic-rich metadata information to describe web services [R5]. Homogeneous access is then facilitated through advanced software that adopts semantic crosswalks for parameter mappings. This enables interoperability with minimum effort, as data providers can maintain their own approaches regarding technologies, metadata standards, and protocols. If necessary, datasets can be converted into a common agreed standard, for example, for visualization on a Graphical User Interface. The semantic information provided by the metadata catalogue and enabled by the interoperability layer is a significant advantage.

2.2. EPOS Platform: an Open-Source Framework for managing Data Services

This combined approach is the result of the collective effort sustained by the European Plate Observing System ERIC⁸ community for the creation of the data portal for Earth Science. The

⁸ <https://www.epos-eu.org/> (accessed 13/06/2025)

EPOS Platform is officially online from 2024 after years of research, development, testing and refining. The Platform supports FAIR principles and is open by design; moreover, its code is made available as an open source project on Github⁹ under a GLPv3 license.

The ENVRI community experimented with the use of the EPOS open source for collecting data services in previous projects, in particular, the CoS entered into the ENVRI-Hub as a result of the ENVRI FAIR project. The architecture of the EPOS platform is based on microservices that compose a four-layer structure. Starting from the outer layer, we have:

- **The Graphical User Interface (GUI)**
Data, data products and services integrated within the platform can be accessed by means of a map-based GUI. It includes search, filtering, download, pre-visualisation;
- **Integrated Core Services – Central Hub system (ICS-C)**
It includes several microservice applications that steer the whole system. The main modules are the metadata database and the API layer;
- **Interoperability layer**
Service providers give access to metadata through APIs with several different standards in terms of protocols, data and metadata format. This layer deals with homogenization by collecting the description of services in the EPOS-DCAT-AP format, by ingesting this information into the central metadata catalogue and eventually converting metadata and data;
- **External Source Services**
In the EPOS framework, the services are grouped into Thematic Core Services (TCSs) that focus on specific disciplines in Earth Science. In EHN, there is not yet such a clusterization, all external services are grouped together.

More details about the architecture of the EPOS platform can be found in the EPOS website¹⁰.

2.3. Developing CoS using the EPOS Open-Source Platform

The CoS is completely interoperable with respect to the EPOS Platform, and, technically, all the services collected within the second one could be easily replicated in the EH. However, considering that the current project focuses on ECVs, we preferred an incremental approach instead of a bulk ingestion (which, furthermore, would have a questionable added value, being a mere duplication of an already existing portal).

Using the EPOS open source platform, CoS made some ad hoc improvements designed and implemented exclusively for the EH. The interaction with the partners, in particular through the User-Facing Layer Task Force established within the EHN consortium, and with potential users raised the need for features dedicated to ECVs. In the first half of the project, we worked on:

- A filter to highlight services related to selected EXVs;
- Pre-configured, shareable thematic views of the portal;

⁹ <https://github.com/epos-eu/epos-open-source>

¹⁰ <https://www.epos-eu.org/>

- Customized API to better serve the Analytical Framework.

The filter allows users to select one or more ECVs and visualize only the related services among all the available ones. This helps in finding and accessing the desired services and, through them, the associated data. The link between a service and its EXVs is encoded via the metadata description; we supplemented the EPOS-DCAT-AP metadata profile with a dedicated entry in the Dataset entity to serve the purpose: `schema:variableMeasured`.

Figure 2: ECV Filter Mockup

The CoS GUI provides a sharing feature. A user can obtain a custom URL to share the current settings of the portal, including the selected services, filters, special configurations and so on. This feature allows us to create a collection of pre-defined templates showing interesting data and/or serving training purposes.

Figure 3: ECV Templates Mockup

In coordination with WP13, we maintained and documented the set of APIs of the CoS. More details regarding the integration of the CoS with the AF are provided in the deliverable D7.2. Deliverable D7.3 instead contains a quick user guide for the CoS GUI. Moreover, the Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) service developed in WP11 (called ENVRI-ID in milestone M18) has been integrated into the GUI and the back-end.

3. Metadata Collection

3.1. Catalogue of Services Metadata

The service database of the CoS consists of a collection of RDF resources serialized in Turtle format, each describing metadata related to datasets and the associated web services that provide access to them. The metadata conforms to the EPOS-DCAT-AP specification[R2]. EPOS-DCAT-AP is an application profile that extends the DCAT-AP specification, which was developed to support the sharing of metadata about catalogues, datasets, and data services across Europe. EPOS-DCAT-AP was originally developed to meet the specific requirements of the EPOS research infrastructure in the solid Earth domain. This profile has since reached a level of maturity and stability that allows it to be adopted in different contexts.

These metadata records are made available via a RESTful API, which can be consumed by a graphical user interface (GUI). The GUI, leveraging the metadata information, allows users to dynamically construct queries to the web services by configuring the relevant parameters. When applicable—specifically, when the service response is in GeoJSON format or a data conversion plug-in is provided—the GUI is capable of rendering the results on an interactive map.

The GUI currently in use is the one adopted by the EPOS Research Infrastructure and made available as an open-source repository. However, during the project, the specific requirements of the ENVRI-Hub NEXT community were collected and continuously monitored; a first set of improvements entered the first deployment, as described in this deliverable, while others are planned for the second part of the project. Regarding metadata harmonization for instance, in the ENVRI-Hub context it is essential to collect information about the measured variables associated with each dataset. To support this requirement, the partners agreed to enrich the EPOS-DCAT-AP profile by adding the property *schema:variableMeasured* to the *dcat:Dataset* entity.

3.2. Maintenance and Growth

WP7 is responsible for the development and the growth (measured by the number of integrated services, that is a KPI of the project) of the CoS; it led and coordinated the activities during the monthly meetings. Moreover, three hackathon-like events provided a boost to all WP tasks:

- A first in-person meeting in Lecce (Italy) in October 2024 focused on the metadata structure and on the CoS architecture¹¹;
- An online training in November 2024 taught the partners on the ingestion procedure in the CoS (and parallelly also in the Fair Data Points)¹²;
- An in-person meeting in Amsterdam (April 2025) refined the connection between the CoS and other EHN services and proposed several improvements for the Graphical User Interface¹³.

¹¹ <https://indico.eqi.eu/event/6441/sessions/5205/>

¹² <https://indico.eqi.eu/event/6589/>

¹³ <https://indico.eqi.eu/event/6647/>

In addition to those events, the CoS development benefited from an architecture webinar (June 2024) where all architectural components of the HUB, including CoS, were presented for consensus and two All-Hands Meetings (June 2025) to assess the relation between CoS and other components through dedicated user journeys.

As of today, the CoS includes metadata of 77 web services, which are highly heterogeneous. Some services provide direct access to data, while others act as links to external portals. The majority of these services (71) were inherited from the ENVRI-FAIR project. Since the start of the ENVRI-Hub NEXT project, the number of available services has increased by six units:

- Four new services: IOC Sealevel Monitoring Station List (as OGC WMS layer), ACTRIS REST API - List of Metadata serving Aerosols ECV, ACTRIS REST API - List of Metadata serving Clouds ECV, EISCAT Madrigal;
- Three services replaced five old instances from SeaDataNet: CDI SPARQL Endpoint, EDMO SPARQL Endpoint, EDMERP SPARQL Endpoint.

3.3. Collaborations with other WPs and Future Steps

Besides WP7, two cross-WP task forces contributed to the design and implementation of the CoS: the ECV Task Force and the User-Facing layer one.

The ECV TF aims to coordinate the efforts toward a homogenized access to Essential Variables, which is one of the objectives of the whole EHN project. The main contribution of the TF to the CoS in this first half of the project is the introduction of the I-Adopt framework that provides a unified vocabulary for the EVs. The framework will be integrated in the CoS in the second half of the project, but the technical feasibility has been assessed by means of a Jupyter notebook that uses the CoS API and the I-Adopt ones. The notebooks are temporarily listed as services within the CoS, so that users can easily reach and use them.

An in-depth analysis of metadata harmonization considering the role of controlled vocabularies is presented in D11.2, which collected several contributions from the ECV TF and WP7. Future development efforts will aim at enhancing the quality, completeness, and interoperability of the service metadata, as well as improving the discoverability and usability of the catalogue overall.

The User-facing layer task force, as the name suggests, focuses on improving the usability of the services of the hub. It represents the counterpart of the technical activities carried on in the different WPs. The mission of this task force is to coordinate the collection of feedback and user requirements for the ENVRI-Hub's frontend, it created a user forum and performed internal and external surveys. The task force findings were reported during the Amsterdam hackathon, a session on UI/UX provided the input for the CoS GUI improvements described in Section 2.3. The collaboration between WP7 and this TF will continue during the whole project.

The collaboration with WP13 on the connection between the CoS and the AF is documented in D7.2. The API provided by the CoS fits well with the architecture of the AF as proved by the deployment of the first release of the EHN. Further improvements are envisioned for the homogenization of data access and for providing the users with an interactive and computationally powerful analysis environment through Virtual Research Environments (VREs).

3.4. Back Office

In the current release of the open-source EPOS Platform, the metadata description of web services is managed manually through Turtle files. Contributors are required to modify service descriptions using the EPOS-DCAT-AP extension of DCAT-AP. These metadata files are then ingested into the internal metadata database via the Ingestor service, which provides an endpoint to add new metadata entries to the catalog.

This manual process presents several limitations that hinder both service integration and platform evolution:

- The Ingestor service currently supports only the addition of metadata. It does not allow editing or deletion of existing records. As a result, modifying metadata requires a full redeployment of the application;
- Users must manually edit the EPOS-DCAT-AP descriptions. This task is complex due to the learning curve associated with the Turtle syntax, and it is prone to human error despite the availability of validation tools;
- Any modification to the metadata necessitates the deletion and reinitialization of the metadata database;
- Metadata management is conducted through a private GitLab repository. Users must submit changes via pull requests, which are reviewed manually by Metadata Curators. These curators test the updates in custom environments before approving them. Once accepted, changes are queued for inclusion in the next platform redeployment cycle.

To overcome these challenges, we envisaged the development of a new component called the Backoffice. This web-based interface works in conjunction with a new backend service to enable direct manipulation of the metadata deployed in any given environment. The system incorporates a robust model of groups, users, and objects to ensure secure and structured metadata management.

Through the Backoffice interface, users can create, edit, and delete service descriptions using an intuitive graphical interface specifically designed for this purpose. This eliminates the need to interact directly with Turtle files or the EPOS-DCAT-AP specification. Once changes are made, they appear in a dedicated preview section of the portal, accessible only to authorized users. After verifying that the updates function correctly, users can submit them for review. Upon approval by a Metadata Curator, the changes are immediately reflected in the main portal without requiring a new ingestion cycle.

The development of the Backoffice is concluded, and it has been released in the staging environment, allowing for testing and feedback from early users in the EPOS community. The open-source edition of EPOS software has been adopted and serves ENVRI CoS.

This modernized approach significantly simplifies metadata management for users and enables administrators to track changes in a continuous and streamlined manner. It removes the need for manual redeployments and supports a more agile and collaborative development process. This facilitates the inclusion of new services in the CoS as requested by the aforementioned requirements.

4. Back-end Operations: API and Data Conversion

This section describes two of the most important back-end features of the CoS, namely the converters and the APIs. The former are responsible for properly rendering the payload of the services on the map-based user interface. The latter are the machine-to-machine interfaces of the catalogue, which are used by the CoS GUI itself, but also by the Analytical Framework and possibly other hub components.

4.1. Converter Component

4.1.1. Overview

The Converter is a key architectural component responsible for transforming payloads retrieved from external services into formats interpretable by the CoS GUI. Given that the catalogue neither controls these external services nor enforces a fixed payload format, the Converter ensures flexibility by enabling on-the-fly conversion of data before it reaches the GUI layer. This conversion is handled dynamically at request time, allowing the frontend to visualize data regardless of the original payload structure. The Converter achieves this by using a plugin-based system where each plugin encapsulates the logic required to transform a specific data format.

4.1.2. Converter Applicability

A converter plugin is only necessary for services whose payloads are not natively supported by the CoS GUI. As of now, the GUI fully supports the following formats or service types:

- WMS (Web Map Service);
- WFS (Web Feature Service);
- GeoJSON;
- CoverageJSON (CovJSON);
- Extended GeoJSON (EPOS GeoJSON)¹⁴: a custom extension of the GeoJSON format that adds specific properties to enhance data visualization in the CoS GUI.

If a service returns data in any of the supported formats listed above, no conversion is required. The converter component is specifically intended to make external services interoperable with the CoS ecosystem without enforcing any data standard. It acts as a bridge for integrating services that provide payloads in alternative or proprietary formats by converting them into a format the GUI can handle.

¹⁴ <https://epos-eu.github.io/epos-open-source/#/epos-geo-json>

4.1.3. Architecture

The Converter component is composed of two microservices: the *converter-routine* and the *converter-service*. These services work together to manage plugin lifecycle, execution, and integration with the broader CoS system.

The *converter-routine* service is focused on plugin provisioning. It ensures that plugin code is available and up-to-date in the execution environment by interacting with remote Git repositories. It adheres to the microservice principle of single responsibility and performs the following tasks:

- Plugin Retrieval and Sync: Every 5 minutes, a scheduled cron job iterates through the list of registered plugins. For each plugin:
 - If the plugin is not already present, it is cloned from its Git repository;
 - If it is already present, a git pull operation is performed to update it;
 - For Python plugins, dependencies are resolved and installed based on a `requirements.txt` file.
- Versioning Support: The routine supports two Git versioning strategies:
 - Branch: The plugin version is interpreted as a branch name;
 - Tag: The version corresponds to a Git tag.
- Supported Plugin Types:
 - Java/Kotlin: Precompiled JAR files;
 - Python: Source files with a `requirements.txt` if needed;
 - Binary: Any self-contained executable compiled for Linux x86.
- Exposed APIs: The *converter-routine* provides endpoints for plugin management at the file system level:
 - Clean;
 - Reinstall;
 - Sync.

The converter service handles the actual execution of conversion plugins when triggered by a request to an external service. It integrates with a *RabbitMQ* message queue to process conversion tasks asynchronously. Its workflow can be summarized as follows:

- The *external access service* receives a request that requires payload conversion;
- The service fetches the original payload and publishes a message to *RabbitMQ*, including the payload and the ID of the plugin to be used;
- The converter service consumes the message, invokes the appropriate plugin on the payload, and sends the converted result back to the access service via *RabbitMQ*.

The plug-in *Execution Interface* performs the following operations:

- Each plugin must be executable from the command line and conform to a simple interface;
- The service invokes the plugin with the following arguments:
 - Custom arguments: As defined in the plugin's metadata (e.g., main class for Java);
 - Input file path: Path to a file containing the original payload;
 - Output file path: Path where the plugin must write the converted result. Example execution:


```
./my-plugin --main-class MyClass input.json output.json
```

The service is responsible for creating the input file and cleaning up temporary files post-execution. Plugins should only read from the input file and write the result to the output file path provided, creating it if it does not exist. The converter service also exposes a set of administrative APIs to:

- Perform CRUD (Create, Read, Update, and Delete) operations on plugins;
- Manage plugin-to-distribution relationships;
- These APIs are currently used manually but are fully compatible with future back-office integration.

4.1.4. Plugin Management

Plugins are described via a metadata model and stored in a centralized plugin catalogue as a separate schema in the main metadata database. The following API can be used to register a new plugin:

```
{
  "arguments": "string", // Custom execution arguments
                        (excluding input/output paths)
  "description": "string", // Plugin description
  "enabled": true, // Whether the plugin is active
  "executable": "string", // Entry point: JAR file, Python main
                        script, or binary name
  "name": "string", // Plugin name
  "repository": "string", // Git URL hosting the plugin
  "runtime": "binary", // One of: 'java', 'python', 'binary'
  "version_type": "branch", // 'branch' or 'tag'
  "version": "string" // Git branch or tag name
}
```

Once a plugin is registered, it can be associated with one or more distributions (a web service) using the following relation model:

```
{
```

```
"input_format": "string", // MIME type of the original payload
"output_format": "string", // MIME type of the converted payload
"plugin_id": "string", // Plugin ID from the catalogue
"relation_id": "string" // Distribution instance ID
}
```

This association enables on-the-fly conversion for any access request targeting that distribution. The original payload remains accessible to the GUI in addition to the converted version.

4.2. CoS APIs

The RESTful APIs are the primary mechanism for programmatic interaction with the CoS, enabling everything from data discovery in the main portal to complex, automated scientific workflows. A complete, publicly documented list of every single endpoint is available in a single document on the Swagger Page: <https://catalogue.staging.envri.eu/api/v1/ui/>.

The API's design and functionality can be robustly inferred from the system's architecture, its adherence to REST principles, and its explicit goal of integrating heterogeneous services. The ENVRI Catalogue of Services API ecosystem is not a single, monolithic interface but a federated system of APIs operating at different architectural layers.

4.2.1. A Federated API Ecosystem: RIs and CoS APIs

Understanding the Catalogue of Services API landscape requires recognizing its two-level structure, which mirrors the federated architecture of the Delivery Framework:

- **RIs APIs:** These are the "source" APIs, exposed by each of the service providers (RIs). They provide machine-readable and machine-actionable access to the harmonized data, products, and services specific to their scientific domain. A developer seeking deep, domain-specific functionality might interact directly with a service API;
- **CoS API:** This is the central, unified API exposed by the Catalogue of Services. It serves as the primary endpoint for end-users and general-purpose applications like the ENVRI Hub. Its purpose is to provide aggregated search and discovery capabilities across *all* integrated RIs.

The CoS API functions as an "API of APIs". It abstracts away the complexity of the dozen or more underlying RIs APIs. A user does not need to learn the specific query syntax or endpoint structure for each scientific community. Instead, they interact with the single CoS API, which handles the task of querying the relevant RIs in the background, aggregating the results, and returning them in a single, coherent, and harmonized response. This abstraction is the core value proposition of the CoS and is what makes true multidisciplinary data discovery possible.

4.2.2. Applying RESTful Principles to the ENVRI Context

The design of the ENVRI CoS API aligns with the standard principles and best practices of the Representational State Transfer (REST) architectural style, which emphasizes statelessness, a uniform interface, and resource-based interactions.

- **Resource-Oriented URLs:** RESTful APIs use nouns to identify resources. The CoS API endpoints are therefore structured around the entities they represent, such as [/dataproducs](#), [/webservices](#), [/organizations](#), and [/distributions](#). These resources are organized hierarchically, allowing for intuitive navigation. For instance, [/dataproducs/{id}](#) would refer to a specific dataset, and a path like [/execute/{id}](#) could be used to scope queries to a particular thematic community;
- **HTTP Verbs for Actions:** The action to be performed on a resource is defined by the standard HTTP method used in the request. For the CoS API, this mapping is critical:
 - **GET:** Used to retrieve resources. This is the primary method for all data discovery operations, such as fetching a list of datasets ([GET /dataproducs](#)) or a single item ([GET /dataproducs/{id}](#));
 - **POST, PUT, DELETE:** These methods, which correspond to create, update, and delete operations, are less likely to be exposed to general end-users for data manipulation. Instead, they would be used by authenticated and authorized personnel, such as TCS managers in EPOS, to submit new metadata descriptions to the ICS catalogue or to update existing ones.
- **Stateless Communication:** As per REST principles, every request sent to the ENVRI CoS API must be self-contained and include all necessary information for the server to process it. The server does not maintain any client session state between requests, which enhances scalability and reliability;
- **JSON as the Standard Data Format:** In line with modern web practices, the ENVRI CoS API uses JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) as the primary format for both request payloads and response bodies. JSON is lightweight, human-readable, and easily parsed by virtually all programming languages. API responses will correctly use the [Content-Type: application/json](#) header to ensure clients interpret the data correctly.
- **Standard HTTP Status Codes:** The API communicates the outcome of a request using standard HTTP status codes. This allows client applications to reliably handle success and failure scenarios. Expected codes include [200 OK](#) for a successful [GET](#) request, [201 Created](#) for a successful [POST](#), and various error codes like [400 Bad Request](#) for invalid input, [401 Unauthorized](#) for missing or invalid credentials, [404 Not Found](#) when a resource does not exist, and [5xx](#) codes for server-side errors.

4.2.3. Inferred API Functionality: A User's Perspective

Based on the system's requirements, a developer interacting with the ENVRI CoS API can expect a rich set of functionalities designed to facilitate powerful data discovery and access.

- **Discovery and Filtering:** The core function of the API is discovery. This is enabled through robust filtering capabilities implemented as query parameters in [GET](#) requests. A developer could construct a query like: [GET /api/v1/search?q=volcano&bbox=10,40,20,50&startDate=2020-01-01&endDate=2021-01-01](#) to find all datasets related to the word "volcano" within a specific geographic bounding box and time range;

- **Hypermedia (HATEOAS):** A mature REST API uses hypermedia to make itself more self-descriptive. Following the principle of Hypertext as the Engine of Application State (HATEOAS), responses from the EPOS API would include not just data but also links to related resources and possible actions. For example, a JSON object describing a dataset would contain a link to the API endpoint of its providing organization (e.g., `href: ".../api/v1/details/{id}"`) and, crucially, a link to the actual data download endpoint, which might point to a specific RIs data service. This allows a client application to navigate the API landscape dynamically without hardcoding URLs;
- **Authentication and Authorization:** Access to certain data or functionalities will be protected. The API integrates with the federated AAI system. A client application would first need to go through an authentication flow (e.g., OAuth 2.0) to obtain an access token. This token would then be included in the `Authorization` header of subsequent API requests (e.g., `Authorization: Bearer <token>`) to prove the user's identity and permissions. The EHN project developed a federated AAI system, called ENVRI-ID; a wide adoption of this system will simplify these processes.

5. Conclusions

The first half of the project paved the way for a successful completion of the proposed outcomes. In particular, the Catalogue of Services reached a maturity level sufficiently solid to allow the connection with all required EHN components, so that in the next period, the consortium can continue building its components.

The CoS is built based on the EPOS experience. However, we need to ingest metadata of more services, continue the harmonization work and develop new conversion plug-ins. Moreover, the notebooks and the FDPs, listed among the services, deserve a more prominent and specific position

The connection with the Analytical Framework is well established, as also described in D7.2. The two components have to proceed together in order to further facilitate access to data.

The integration with vocabulary tools like iAdopt¹⁵ has to scale up to the level of the catalogue, since one of the main barriers to interdisciplinary science is the diversity in sectoral language, community practices, and the standards.

The integration of the ENVRI-ID with the CoS GUI and with the back-end has been straightforward, but the propagation to the Backoffice tool is still to be addressed. The Knowledge Base indexing is complete, but only the reference to the EXVs examples can be returned to the user at the moment.

Legal and ethical considerations are out of the scope of the present deliverable, but it's worth noticing in the end that work has been done in both directions. The long-term sustainability of the CoS component, as well as of the entire hub, is under consideration with good perspectives. In particular, the CoS, together with other Hub services, could be exposed to federate with the EOSC during the second part of the project. This will require some further development, as planned in the DoA of the project.

¹⁵ <https://i-adopt.github.io/ontology/>

6. References

References	
No	Description/Link
R1	DCAT Application profile for data portals in Europe (DCAT-AP) https://op.europa.eu/it/web/eu-vocabularies/dcat-ap
R2	EPOS-DCAT-AP: an extension of the DCAT Application Profile for Research Infrastructures in the solid-Earth domain https://www.epos-eu.org/epos-dcat-ap#
R3	Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship . Sci Data 3, 160018 (2016). https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18
R4	Vinciarelli, V., Orfino, A., Paciello, R., Bailo, D., Goffi, C., Giuliacci, K., Sbarra, M., Michalek, J., Nedrebø, H., Roquencourt, J.-B., Retout, Y., Warren, D., and Lavrnja-Czapski, J. EPOS Open Source: A platform for integrating high-quality research product and services . EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24-28 Apr 2023. EGU23-6400. https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-6400
R5	Bailo, D. et al. (2023). Integrated Access to Multidisciplinary Data Through Semantically Interoperable Services in a Metadata-Driven Platform for Solid Earth Science . In: Garoufallou, E., Vlachidis, A. (eds) Metadata and Semantic Research. MTSR 2022. Communications in Computer and Information Science, vol 1789. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-39141-5_20